

LLM-Orchestrated PCB Design: From Schematic Understanding to Placement, Routing, and Iterative Refinement

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Abstract. We propose a method for automated printed circuit board (PCB) design that uses a large language model (LLM) agent to orchestrate the complete layout pipeline: schematic understanding, constraint generation, placement optimization, autorouting, design review, and iterative refinement. The LLM agent is equipped with specialized electronic design automation (EDA) tools that handle data extraction and targeted analysis, while the LLM’s reasoning capacity is reserved for engineering judgment. The agent communicates design intent to a placement optimizer through a structured constraint interchange format, then evaluates physical outcomes (placement quality, routing metrics, constraint satisfaction) and refines its directives in a closed loop. The placement engine builds on CadMust, a PCB CAD suite originally developed in the 1990s for the Acorn RISC OS platform, re-implemented in Python as an open-source KiCad plugin. This report presents the method, its architectural principles, and its claims of novelty. The LLM orchestration layer is in design phase; experimental validation of the complete pipeline is future work. The method is specified in sufficient detail to support reproducibility in principle. The core contribution is the introduction of a large language model as a semantic translation layer between schematic-level design intent and formal placement constraints, closing the gap between design understanding and numerical optimization that has persisted across sixty years of placement research.

1 Background

1.1 Placement optimization methods

Automated placement of electronic components has been studied for over sixty years, beginning with graph embedding approaches in the early 1960s. The field has produced a diverse set of optimization methods:

Simulated annealing (SA), originating with Kirkpatrick et al. [1] and the TimberWolf placement tool [2], minimizes a cost function (typically half-perimeter wirelength, HPWL) subject to overlap and boundary constraints, using stochastic moves with temperature-dependent acceptance. SA remains widely used in both VLSI and PCB placement due to its ability to escape local minima and handle diverse constraint types.

Genetic and evolutionary algorithms encode placements as chromosomes and evolve populations through selection, crossover, and mutation operators. These have been applied to PCB placement in academic work but have seen limited adoption in production EDA tools.

Force-directed placement models compo-

nents and nets as a spring system, iteratively relaxing toward equilibrium. This approach is computationally efficient but can struggle with constraint handling and local minima.

Analytical placement formulates placement as a continuous optimization problem (quadratic or nonlinear), solving for component positions that minimize wirelength subject to density constraints. This is the dominant approach in modern VLSI place-and-route tools but has seen limited application to PCB placement, where the problem structure differs (fewer components, more heterogeneous footprints, mechanical constraints).

Partitioning-based methods (e.g., Fiduccia-Mattheyses min-cut) recursively divide the placement region and component set, producing coarse placements that are refined by other methods.

Reinforcement learning (RL) has been applied to both VLSI and PCB placement. Mirhoseini et al. [3] demonstrated RL-based chip floorplanning at Google, using graph neural networks to encode chip netlists. For PCB specifically, Vassallo [4] explored RL-based component placement. Commercial tools such as Quilter use RL agents

trained on physics simulations to generate placement and routing candidates.

CadMust, developed by Usarc in the early 1990s for the Acorn RISC OS platform [6], implemented SA-based PCB component placement as part of a complete PCB CAD suite. The original optimizer source code (written in C) served as the algorithmic heritage for the present work. CadMust-Neo re-implements and extends these algorithms in pure Python, targeting the KiCad 9/10 EDA platform via its plugin API.

All of these optimization methods share a common characteristic: they operate on connectivity graphs and geometric constraints, minimizing wirelength and satisfying physical rules. None incorporate understanding of design intent: the engineering rationale for *why* components should be grouped, separated, or constrained in particular ways.

1.2 AI approaches to design understanding

A distinct line of work applies AI to understanding circuit designs rather than optimizing placement geometry.

Schematic topology analysis. Some commercial PCB layout tools perform limited automatic detection of common circuit patterns, such as identifying bypass capacitors by their connection between component pins and ground, detecting differential pairs by net naming conventions, recognizing switching converter topologies by inductor-IC connectivity. These detections use fixed pattern-matching rules rather than general reasoning about circuit function.

LLMs in chip design. In the adjacent field of VLSI/IC design, large language models have been applied to RTL code generation, verification, and design assistance (e.g., ChipNeMo [5]). However, chip design operates at a fundamentally different abstraction level (transistor-level logic synthesis) than PCB design (board-level assembly of discrete components), and these methods do not transfer to PCB layout.

LLMs as EDA chat assistants. LLMs have been used as conversational assistants for PCB design, answering questions about components, reviewing schematics via uploaded PDFs or screenshots, and providing general layout advice through chat interfaces. These approaches rely on the LLM parsing raw files or images without structured extraction tools, resulting in unreliable analysis (e.g., false findings about missing compo-

nents that are actually present in the schematic).

MCP servers for KiCad. A growing ecosystem of Model Context Protocol (MCP) servers connects LLMs to EDA tools like KiCad, enabling chat-driven component manipulation and file operations. However, these integrations provide mechanical I/O without engineering reasoning about placement quality or design intent.

The application of LLMs to orchestrate the complete PCB layout pipeline (from schematic understanding through constraint extraction, placement, routing, review, and iterative refinement) has not, to the author’s knowledge, been previously described in published work or publicly available tools.

2 Problem Statement

The gap between schematic capture and quality PCB layout is bridged entirely by manual engineering expertise. An experienced layout engineer reads a schematic and mentally constructs a placement plan: functional groupings, edge-locked connectors, critical signal paths, thermal zones, mechanical constraints from known form factors. This implicit knowledge is not captured in any file exchanged between schematic and layout tools.

The schematic contains rich design intent (hierarchical organization, functional blocks, signal relationships, power topology) that is lost during netlist export to the PCB editor. The board file retains only connectivity (which pads connect to which nets) without the engineering rationale for why components should be grouped, separated, or constrained.

Current auto-placement tools primarily treat placement as an optimization problem over connectivity graphs and physical rules. Some incorporate limited schematic understanding through fixed pattern-matching rules. However, these detections cover a narrow set of common patterns and do not extend to general reasoning about design intent: that an EMI filter requires specific trace routing, that a board matches a known form factor specification, or that a charge pump topology demands a particular component arrangement for loop area minimization.

The problem is broader than placement alone. A complete PCB layout requires placement, routing, and iterative review. Each stage produces physical outcomes that may reveal issues invisible at the previous stage: a placement that looks good may produce unroutable bottlenecks; a routed

board may have EMC issues that require placement changes. Human engineers iterate between these stages using judgment. No publicly described automated system closes this loop with engineering reasoning.

3 Proposed Method

The method is a complete LLM-orchestrated PCB design pipeline comprising six stages (Figure 1). The LLM agent participates actively in stages 1, 2, 5, and 6. Stages 3 and 4 are executed by numerical optimizers and autorouters. The constraint file serves as the explicit, inspectable communication mechanism between the LLM’s design understanding and the optimization engines.

A fundamental design principle is that the engineer remains in control at every stage. The pipeline is not a black box that consumes a schematic and produces a finished board. At each stage, the engineer can inspect the intermediate outputs, modify them, override the LLM’s decisions, or take over manually. The LLM is an assistant that handles tedious analysis and optimization work; the engineer retains authority over all design decisions. This human-in-the-loop architecture ensures that domain expertise, institutional knowledge, and design judgment that the LLM may lack can be applied at any point in the process.

3.1 Schematic understanding

The LLM agent builds a comprehensive understanding of the design by reading and reasoning about the schematic. Rather than ingesting raw schematic files (which are verbose with rendering information irrelevant to design intent), the agent uses a pre-processing step and targeted tool calls.

Schematic pre-processing. A standalone tool extracts engineering-relevant information from schematic files: hierarchical sheet structure, component lists, net connections, cross-sheet references, power topology, differential pair annotations, and designer notes. The output is a structured summary that preserves the engineer’s organizational intent (sheet hierarchy reflects functional decomposition) while discarding rendering details. This pre-processor operates directly on schematic file formats without requiring the EDA application itself.

Agent-driven analysis. The LLM calls specialized tool functions on demand to investigate specific aspects of the design: tracing a net across hierarchical sheets, mapping power distribution

trees from regulators to loads, identifying differential pairs by naming convention and topology, detecting bypass capacitor associations, recognizing switching converter topologies, identifying board form factors from outline geometry and connector pinouts, or querying board-level properties.

The key principle is that small, optimized functions extract and summarize specific design information far more efficiently than an LLM parsing raw files. The LLM’s context window is reserved for design reasoning and engineering judgment, not data extraction. The specific set of tools, their interfaces, and their implementation may vary; the method is defined by the separation of extraction (tools) from reasoning (LLM).

The engineer can participate in this stage by guiding the LLM’s analysis (e.g., “this section is a battery management system, pay attention to cell balancing”), correcting misidentifications, or providing context that is not present in the schematic files (e.g., mechanical constraints from the enclosure, thermal requirements from the operating environment).

3.2 Constraint generation

The LLM synthesizes its design understanding into a structured constraint file (e.g., JSON) that serves as the explicit, human-inspectable interface between the LLM’s reasoning and the placement optimizer. The constraint format is input-agnostic: constraints may originate from LLM analysis, manual engineering input, or other automated tools.

The constraint format expresses categories of placement intent including but not limited to: functional component groupings with proximity limits, net priority tiers for wirelength weighting, edge-locked connector positions, preferred placement zones, keepout areas, fixed positions, back-side placement, and free-text design notes. Figures 2–4 show representative examples from a hand-written ground truth constraint file for a 170-component development board.

Figure 1: The LLM-orchestrated PCB design pipeline. Purple stages are driven by LLM reasoning; blue stages by numerical optimization. The engineer (green) can inspect and modify outputs at every stage, including candidate selection from multiple optimizer runs. The dashed loop represents iterative constraint refinement based on design review.

```
{
  "id": "voltage_reg",
  "name": "3.3V Buck Regulator",
  "rationale": "Minimize switching loop area (VIN-SW-L-VOUT) for EMI compliance",
  "members": ["U2", "L1", "C5", "C8", "C9"],
  "max_span_mm": 15.0,
  "template": {
    "anchor": "U2",
    "relative_positions": {
      "L1": {"dx_mm": 4, "dy_mm": 0, "pin_affinity": "SW"},
      "C5": {"dx_mm": -3, "dy_mm": 2, "pin_affinity": "VIN"},
      "C8": {"dx_mm": 4, "dy_mm": 2, "pin_affinity": "VOUT"}
    }
  }
}
```

Figure 2: Component group constraint for a buck regulator. The `template` field specifies relative positions anchored to the regulator IC, keeping the switching loop tight. The `rationale` field preserves the engineering reasoning for human review.

```
{
  "edge_locked": [
    {"ref": "J1", "edge": "left", "rationale": "DC barrel jack"},
    {"ref": "J2", "edge": "right", "rationale": "RJ45 Ethernet jack"},
    {"ref": "J3", "edge": "bottom", "rationale": "USB programming port"},
    {"ref": "J4", "edge": "top", "rationale": "Expansion header"}
  ],
  "zone_preferences": [
    {"ref": "U4", "zone": "center-right", "rationale": "Ethernet PHY near RJ45"},
    {"ref": "U1", "zone": "center", "rationale": "MCU, central position"}
  ]
}
```

Figure 3: Placement constraints for edge-locked connectors and zone preferences. Edge-locked components are fixed to board edges; zone preferences are soft constraints guiding the optimizer.

```

{
  "net_priorities": {
    "critical": {
      "nets": ["ETH_TXD0", "ETH_TXD1",
               "ETH_RXD0", "ETH_RXD1",
               "ETH_CRS_DV", "ETH_REFCLK"],
      "weight": 3.0,
      "rationale": "50 MHz Ethernet bus,
                    length
                    matching and short traces required"
    },
    "high": {
      "nets": ["USB_D+", "USB_D-",
               "SD_CLK", "SD_CMD"],
      "weight": 2.0,
      "rationale": "USB diff pair + SD bus"
    },
    "exclude": {
      "nets": ["GND", "+3.3V", "+5V",
               "VBUS", "VBAT"],
      "rationale": "Power planes, not routed
                    as traces"
    }
  }
}

```

Figure 4: Net priority tiers for HPWL weighting. Critical nets (RMII Ethernet bus) receive $3\times$ weight, encouraging shorter traces. Power nets are excluded from wirelength optimization entirely.

The specific schema and categories may evolve; the method is defined by the use of an explicit, structured, inspectable constraint representation as the contract between design analysis and placement optimization.

Because the constraint file is structured and human-readable, the engineer can review, edit, add, or remove any constraint before optimization begins. This is the primary point of human oversight: the engineer inspects what the LLM understood about the design and corrects any errors or adds knowledge that the LLM missed. The constraint file can also be versioned, diffed, and reused across design revisions.

Before submitting constraints to the optimizer, the LLM may analyze the constraint set for mutual satisfiability: identifying conflicts (e.g., two groups competing for the same board region), redundancies, or physically infeasible directives given board geometry and component dimensions.

3.3 Placement optimization

The placement optimizer (whether SA-based, RL-based, or using other methods) consumes the constraint file and incorporates its directives into the optimization objective. Constraint-derived penalty terms or hard constraints guide the optimizer toward placements that satisfy design intent, not just minimize wirelength. The optimizer may generate multiple candidate placements for

comparison. The engineer can pre-place or lock specific components before optimization (e.g., connectors at board edges, mounting holes at fixed positions), and the optimizer respects these as hard constraints.

3.4 Routing

An autorouter (such as Freerouting or similar tools) routes the placed board. Routing is a necessary step before meaningful design review, because many layout quality issues (signal integrity, EMC, manufacturability) only become apparent in the routed result.

3.5 Design review

The LLM evaluates the physical outcomes of placement and routing against the original design intent. This review goes beyond numerical constraint satisfaction scoring (which is also performed): the LLM reasons about whether the physical result achieves the engineering goals that motivated the constraints.

Review considerations include but are not limited to: whether critical signal paths are short and direct, whether switching converter loops are tight enough for EMI compliance, whether thermal dissipation paths are adequate, whether the routing respects impedance requirements, whether there are unrouted nets or routing bottlenecks that indicate placement problems, and whether the overall layout is manufacturable.

The LLM can distinguish between constraints that were satisfied but produced poor results (indicating the constraint was wrong or incomplete) and constraints that were violated (indicating the optimizer needs different parameters or more iterations). The engineer can review the LLM’s assessment, accept or reject individual findings, and add observations from their own inspection of the physical layout.

3.6 Iterative refinement

Based on the design review, the LLM diagnoses deficiencies and generates revised constraints for subsequent optimization. The refinement loop distinguishes between:

- **Under-constrained** designs: missing constraints that would prevent observed issues (e.g., no group constraint on a switching converter whose components ended up scattered)
- **Over-constrained** designs: constraints that conflict or prevent the optimizer from finding feasible solutions

- **Mischaracterized** constraints: correct intent but wrong parameters (e.g., group span too tight or too loose)

The LLM generates revised constraints and the pipeline iterates (stages 2 through 5), enabling convergence toward design intent without human intervention. The designer may intervene at any iteration to inspect, modify, or approve the constraint set.

4 Architecture: Heritage and Modernization

The SA placement core of this system descends from CadMust [6], a PCB CAD suite developed by Usarc in the early 1990s for the Acorn Archimedes and RISC PC platforms running RISC OS. CadMust included schematic capture, PCB layout with manual and automated placement, and autorouting capabilities. The placement optimizer used simulated annealing with HPWL minimization, overlap avoidance, and boundary enforcement.

CadMust-Neo preserves the algorithmic foundation (SA with adaptive cooling, Metropolis acceptance criterion, translate/swap/rotate moves) while modernizing every aspect of the implementation:

- Pure Python (no compiled dependencies), targeting the KiCad plugin API
- Incremental cost function updates: $O(k)$ per move for k affected nets, $O(\log n + k)$ for overlap detection via sorted bounding box arrays
- Temperature-scaled penalties for boundary and keepout constraints
- Multi-start optimization with greedy refinement
- Power net exclusion from HPWL (automatic detection by name pattern and schematic topology)
- Component group support (rigid-body movement, same-group overlap exclusion)
- Polygon board outline support (non-rectangular boards)

The LLM agent layer is entirely new and has no precedent in the original CadMust system or, to the author’s knowledge, in any publicly described PCB design tool.

5 Differentiation from Existing Approaches

This method differs from existing approaches in several fundamental ways:

1. **Complete pipeline orchestration.** Existing LLM integrations for EDA tools provide mechanical I/O but do not orchestrate the design pipeline with engineering reasoning. Existing auto-layout tools optimize placement or routing, and some perform limited schematic understanding through fixed pattern-matching rules, but none derive placement rationale from general reasoning about circuit function.
2. **Intelligence source.** Design intent understanding comes from an LLM reasoning about the schematic in real time, not from a model trained on historical board designs. The system can handle novel designs, unusual form factors, and domain-specific constraints without retraining.
3. **Transparency.** The constraint file is a fully inspectable intermediate representation. The designer can read, edit, and override any constraint before optimization. There is no black-box mapping from schematic to placement.
4. **Closed-loop refinement.** The LLM evaluates physical outcomes (not just numerical metrics) and refines its own constraint generation based on what worked and what did not. This iterative self-correction is distinct from both single-pass optimization and human-in-the-loop iteration.
5. **Decomposition.** The pipeline stages are cleanly separated by explicit interfaces. Each stage can be used independently, improved independently, or replaced independently. The constraint interchange format decouples the intelligence layer from the optimization layer.
6. **Human-in-the-loop at every stage.** The engineer can inspect, modify, and override at every pipeline stage: guiding schematic analysis, editing constraints before optimization, pre-placing components, reviewing placement candidates, and accepting or rejecting the LLM’s design review findings. The system augments engineering expertise rather than replacing it.
7. **Open integration.** The system operates as a plugin within an existing open-source EDA tool (KiCad), preserving the designer’s workflow. No proprietary platform or file format is required. The tools and constraint format can be exposed via open protocols (such as the Model Context Protocol) for use by any LLM agent.

6 Implementation Status

This report is a method disclosure, not an experimental study. The placement optimizer is implemented and benchmarked; the LLM orchestration layer is in design phase. Experimental validation of the complete pipeline, including comparison of LLM-generated constraints against hand-written constraints and unassisted optimization, is planned as future work.

As of April 2026:

- The SA optimizer is implemented and functional, with 40 unit tests and a 76-board benchmark corpus showing average 52.6% HPWL improvement over unoptimized initial placement.
- The constraint JSON schema (v1) is defined and validated.
- A hand-written ground truth constraint file for a 170-component development board demonstrates the expressiveness of the constraint format (Figures 2–4).
- The schematic pre-processor and LLM agent are in design phase, with the architecture documented in this report.
- The autorouter integration and review loop are in design phase.
- The placement optimizer is released as open-source software under the MIT license. The LLM agent and associated tools described in this report will be released under the same license as they are implemented.

Planned evaluation will compare constraint-augmented placement against unassisted SA optimization and hand-written ground truth constraints, measuring impact on HPWL, routing completion rate, DRC violation count, and functional group cohesion. The correctness and usefulness of LLM-generated constraints will be assessed against expert-written constraint files for boards of varying complexity.

7 Claims of Novelty

The following elements are, to the best of the author’s knowledge, novel and not described in prior art. To be explicit about scope: this work does not claim a new placement optimization algorithm (SA is well-established), does not claim that LLMs can reliably reason about all aspects of PCB design (this requires empirical validation), and does not claim a solved or complete system. The novelty lies in the architecture and method of combining LLM-based design understanding with numer-

Figure 5: *CadMust-Neo optimizer progress dialog during simulated annealing. The temperature gradient bar (top) shows the current SA temperature; the wirelength bar tracks HPWL reduction. This run achieved 15.1% HPWL improvement during the reheating phase.*

ical optimization through a structured constraint interface:

Claim 1: LLM-orchestrated PCB design pipeline

A method for automated PCB design comprising an LLM agent that orchestrates the complete layout pipeline: (i) schematic understanding via pre-processing and targeted tool-based analysis, (ii) structured constraint generation expressing design intent, (iii) constraint-aware placement optimization, (iv) autorouting, (v) LLM-driven design review evaluating physical outcomes against engineering intent, and (vi) iterative constraint refinement based on review findings. The LLM participates in the reasoning-intensive stages while numerical optimizers and autorouters handle the computation-intensive stages, with a structured constraint interchange format as the explicit contract between them.

Claim 2: Zero-shot LLM inference of implicit placement constraints

The use of a general-purpose pre-trained large language model, without domain-specific fine-tuning on EDA training data, to analyze electronic schematic netlists and infer placement constraints by reasoning about circuit function, component relationships, and established PCB design heuristics. The LLM requires no training on historical board layouts or domain-specific datasets; it applies general reasoning augmented by specialized extraction tools (see Claim 3) to infer constraints that are implied by the circuit topol-

ogy but not explicitly annotated in the source schematic. While some existing tools detect specific common patterns (bypass capacitors, differential pairs) through fixed topology-matching rules, this method is designed to enable open-ended reasoning about arbitrary circuit functions, including but not limited to: functional groupings from connectivity subgraphs, switching converter loop tightness from topology detection, board form factor recognition from outline geometry and connector pinout matching, thermal zone identification from power dissipation analysis, and domain-specific constraints that no fixed rule set could anticipate.

Claim 3: Agentic tool-use architecture for electronic design analysis

An agentic LLM architecture for electronic design analysis comprising specialized callable tool functions for targeted design queries, including but not limited to: net connectivity tracing across hierarchical sheets, power distribution tree mapping from regulators to loads, differential signal pair identification, functional group clustering based on connectivity subgraphs, bypass capacitor and switching converter topology detection, board form factor recognition, and schematic pre-processing that converts EDA file formats into token-efficient structured summaries preserving hierarchical design intent, where the LLM autonomously selects and sequences tool invocations to build a design understanding sufficient for constraint generation, and where the LLM’s context is reserved for engineering reasoning rather than data extraction.

Claim 4: Closed-loop design refinement with constraint validation and LLM evaluation of physical outcomes

A closed-loop design refinement method wherein: (i) an LLM generates placement constraints from schematic analysis, (ii) the LLM validates the constraint set for mutual satisfiability given board geometry and component dimensions, identifying conflicts, redundancies, or physically infeasible directives before optimization begins, (iii) a numerical optimizer produces a placement satisfying those constraints, (iv) an autorouter routes the placed board, (v) the LLM evaluates design quality by comparing physical outcomes against engineering intent, (vi) the LLM diagnoses constraint deficiencies (distinguishing between under-constrained, over-constrained, and conflicting con-

straints) and (vii) generates revised constraints for subsequent optimization, with the goal of iterative convergence toward design intent without human intervention.

Claim 5: LLM-driven design review of routed PCBs

A method for automated design review of placed and routed printed circuit boards wherein an LLM evaluates physical layout outcomes against engineering intent. This differs from chat-based design advisory (reviewing schematics via PDF upload or screenshot analysis) in that it evaluates actual physical layout outcomes produced by optimization and routing tools, and produces actionable feedback expressed as constraint modifications (additions, removals, or parameter adjustments) rather than abstract quality scores or conversational advice. Review considerations include but are not limited to: signal path directness and routing topology, switching converter loop area and EMI implications, thermal dissipation adequacy, impedance control compliance, routing bottlenecks indicating placement deficiencies, and manufacturability concerns.

The system architecture incorporates a structured constraint interchange format (e.g., JSON) serving as an explicit, human-inspectable contract between LLM-based design analysis and numerical placement optimization. This format decouples the intelligence layer (constraint generation) from the optimization layer (SA, RL, or other methods), enabling independent development, replacement, or combination of either component. The approach combines modern LLM-based design intent extraction with classical placement algorithms (including simulated annealing techniques dating to the 1980s–90s), where the LLM provides the engineering judgment that classical optimizers lack, and the optimizer provides the mathematical rigor that LLMs cannot perform.

References

- [1] S. Kirkpatrick, C. D. Gelatt, and M. P. Vecchi. Optimization by simulated annealing. *Science*, 220(4598):671–680, 1983. DOI: [10.1126/science.220.4598.671](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.220.4598.671)
- [2] C. Sechen and A. Sangiovanni-Vincentelli. TimberWolf3.2: A new standard cell placement and global routing package. In *Proc. 23rd ACM/IEEE Design Automa-*

- tion Conf.*, pp. 432–439, 1986. researchgate.net/publication/4218625
- [3] A. Mirhoseini, A. Goldie, M. Yazgan, et al. A graph placement methodology for fast chip design. *Nature*, 594(7862):207–212, 2021. DOI: [10.1038/s41586-021-03544-w](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-03544-w)
- [4] L. Vassallo. Automated PCB component placement using reinforcement learning. MSc thesis, University of Malta, 2023. lukevassallo.com (PDF)
- [5] M. Liu, T.-D. Ene, R. Kirby, et al. Chip-NeMo: Domain-adapted LLMs for chip design. *arXiv preprint*, arXiv:2311.00176, 2023. arxiv.org/abs/2311.00176
- [6] CadMust PCB CAD Suite. Usarc, circa 1993. Acorn RISC OS platform.
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This work is published under open access to ensure these methods remain freely available to the electronic design community. The placement optimizer is available under the MIT open-source license at github.com/remiblokker/CadMust-Neo.